

Female mid-career composers' cultural experiences, digital identities, and genre-crossing compositions: a thematic analysis

A paper based on my presentation "The impact of early childhood experiences on the digital identity development of female genre-crossing composers: lives across cultures" at the ERUA symposium "Research Impact of Arts@Matter Cluster"

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Introduction

This paper is an ongoing piece of work with a further data analysis on my presentation at the ERUA symposium (website: erua-eui.eu; please refer to the subtitle), in May 2025. The summer symposium was intertwined with my PhD graduation week, leaving nice memories at the end of my journey as a student. By now, my student identity has been fading away, but as a past school teacher, curriculum designer, teaching director (teacher educator), and a current higher education academic mentor, I keep the habit of learning. Learning has been important for all of my professional roles, so has it been for working educators, musicians, music teachers, and music higher education lecturers.

Social and psychological research has looked extensively into the lives of some professionals mentioned above, but the learning and working environments of people holding other professions, or multiple professions, have been less understood. Moreover, the lives of people working across fields (such as different musical genres) and cultures have been rarely discussed. My paper aims to explore these understudied areas with a thematic analysis conducted in June 2025, entailing the life stories¹ of three female genre-crossing mid-career composers. My discussion follows the line of inquiry "portfolio career"² highlighted in my previous paper (Zheng, 2025), and contributes further understandings to developing supportive social, cultural, and digital environments for women's educational and professional choices and trajectories. My analysis focuses on the impacts of cultural pluralism and intersectionality in the three women's upbringing environments, as well as those on the development of their digital identities and music careers.

Background

An embrace of different cultures resonates with my own learning and working experiences. I grew up in an environment with diverse cultures and acoustic surroundings. Before my postgraduate studies I worked as an all-subjects teacher and

¹ & ² Please refer to **Glossary** for terminologies: portfolio career, life story, and life history.

curriculum designer (full-time), as well as a music performer, writer, and director (part-time) (Zheng, 2024a). Thus, understanding how people develop professionally in different social and cultural contexts has been a part of my career aspiration ever since I was a school student.

This paper uses the original data from my PhD research, the initial scaffolding of which is the classic life history methodology (Zheng, 2022 & 2023). Having conducted multiple rounds of qualitative coding, and developed a digitally-facilitated, multi-layered method of analysis (which includes life history analysis), I configured full life histories of eight female conductor/composer/producer(s) in six countries and across three generations. After writing three full drafts addressing three different analytical directions, I decided to focus on intersectionality which tailors closely to the wider context at the time of my PhD thesis completion (Zheng, 2024c).

Therefore, for writing this paper, in June 2025 I reconfigured life stories of three mid-career female composers for a thematic analysis: Vanora, Xing, and Lydia (pseudonyms). My analysis is without identifiable information due to the research ethics (Zheng, 2025). This paper reveals the interweaving of historical and social influences in the three women's educational and professional lives, paving ways for further suggestions on developing equitable and sustainable learning and working environments in education and industry ecosystems.

Data and Analysis

Vanora

Vanora (pseudonym) is a music composer whose working genres include pop-rock and jazz [play the recording]. Her life story reveals that:

- Vanora's childhood social environment entails cultural diversity and intersectionality. Hence, since early childhood she has been learning four musical instruments, all out of her own interests, and were continuously supported by her family. Her multi-instrumental learning has helped maintaining and developing different social-relations, encouraging the development of a culturally pluralist musical identity.
- At her young adulthood, her family started to hold an inconsistent attitude toward her musical pursuits, which disrupted her motivation for continuous musical learning, and delayed the critical moment for her career establishment.
- When considering the establishment of digital identity, Vanora disliked over-using personal images to garner popularity (Abidin, 2018), because she concerned about the historical narratives that "fantasised" the "innate talents" (skills) yet neglected the endeavours and characteristics, e.g., perseverance, resilience, etc., of the female musicians (Green, 1997; Harries, 2014; Zheng, 2024a). The historical fanaticism (or

worse, ignorance) of women's professional contributions persists the gender biases in contemporary music industries and hinder the female musicians' professional identity development.

- For continuous musical and professional development, Vanora has been learning from her role models online, who are women with cultural minority backgrounds in different occupations and leadership positions. They have become important references for the development of her digital identity and music career.

Xing

Xing (pseudonym) is a classically-trained mid-career composer whose working-genres include indie and experimental music. Currently she also teaches arts programme at higher education institutes [play the recording]. Her life story shows that:

- In "helping" daughters to pursue a specific music profession, some families could incline to adopt a socially prescribed image for the daughter, for example, with particular styles of hair, clothing, or even physical characteristics. These can heavily constrain the girl's autonomy in her early musical development. Previous studies have evidenced the equally harmful impacts of such a family disorientation on boys' childhood musical development (Einarsdottir, 2022; Freer, 2009). These indicate that across the different childhood environments, roots of traditions can be reproduced through daily practices, hindering or facilitating the creative development of girls or boys living in various social-cultural contexts (Hallam, 2017; Hill, 2018). In the cases of Vanora and Xing, the effects of the traditions depend largely on the educational practices of the family or other primary carers.
- Hence, when childhood environment lacks (awareness of) cultural diversity, it can compromise learning motivation and persistence, hurdle (long-term) identity development, and reduce the possibility for developing successful careers at adulthood. Having been aware of this lack in her upbringing environment, Xing has been advocating for equality, diversity, and inclusion in her various living contexts, the details of which were illustrated in my previous paper (Zheng, 2025).
- Because her intersectional experiences, Xing has admired women with less gender-conforming artistry and resisted singular or routinised ways of musical practices. These have been integrated into her digital identity. Similar to Vanora, Xing avoided promoting personal images online for career purposes. This confirms the aforementioned cross-cultural phenomenon, i.e., historical fanaticism or ignorance (Green, 1997; Harries, 2014; Zheng, 2024a), that have been discrediting women's authentic experiences in music professions. Therefore, Xing has been using comprehensive digital technologies to demonstrate social and artistic expressions and skills in her compositions and lectures. She also actively facilitates cross-cultural

collaborations with contemporary art exhibitions (Zheng, 2025). This evidences strong creativity in her portfolio career encompassing professional development in music, education, and visual arts.

Lydia

Lydia (pseudonym) is a genre-crossing composer who is also teaching in a music conservatoire and leading a jazz band. Her story highlights the support of her family and music teachers [play the recording]:

- Lydia enjoyed non-judgemental learning environments at home and at her childhood music lessons. Among the three female composers, Lydia's family held a most consistent and supportive attitude toward her musical learning, creating a home environment where she could enjoy music free play and improvisatory practices. Also, at early childhood, Lydia studied music comprehensively under the guidance of a piano teacher who "gave (student) a great foundation", made the class "like a game", and arranged a repertoire with pieces of "classical piano" and "(others with) jazz influence(s)". In other words, the teacher used "inclusive pedagogies" balancing the cultural traditions and the personal interests of the student (Maclean, 2023, cited in Zheng, 2025), which Lydia appreciates greatly.
- Lydia dislikes using personal images for professional advancement even more than Vanora, "If I wasn't a professional musician, I would be very tempted to delete all (my) social media". This fear results from a historically-inherited "canon" in music (Citron, 1993), i.e., a social construction where "a pre-existent entity" determines the types of music that can persist over time (ibid., p. 17). The musical canon only recognises "a specified group or a body of related works" (ibid.) in determination of the conventional aesthetics in music, perpetuating "meritocratic elitism" and casting fears over the developing musicians in contemporary music ecosystems (Väkevä et al., 2022, cited in Zheng, 2025). Existing studies have bespoke this topic (Citron, 1993; Green, 1997; Harries, 2014; etc.), providing extensive evidences of the historical canon's harmful effects. The most significant effect for musicians with less advantaged backgrounds, including women, cultural minorities, gender minorities, or young musicians, can be their psychological well-beings (e.g., ISME, 2012).
- Hence, even with supportive family, music teachers, and a non-judgmental childhood environment, after career establishment, Lydia still encountered historically-inherited gendering cultures ("canons") at her two working genres – classical and jazz music. Moreover, she has encountered challenges for time and band management even from before her career establishment (at undergraduate). These historical canons and contemporary challenges have catalysed the prevalence of "portfolio careers" discussed in my previous paper (Zheng, 2025). With changes in the wider social and

professional environments, navigating portfolio careers has become increasingly important for music professionals. People with less advantaged backgrounds are faced with more difficulties for achieving work-life balances, cultivating sustainable careers, or upholding psychological well-beings (Alarifi et al., 2024; ISME, 2012; Zheng, 2025).

Conclusion

The thematic analysis presented above evidences the impacts of historical and social factors on the career establishment, development, and sustainability of contemporary mid-career female composers, Vanora, Xing, and Lydia (pseudonym), with living and working experiences in four countries and five music genres. My analysis proves that childhood family and wider social environment play significant roles in shaping the early trajectories of musical learning. In addition, endorsing fixated social images and inconsistent family attitudes hinder long-term musical and career development. Hence, a positive learning environment in music entails safeguarding children and youngsters from partial evaluations and discriminative judgment, embracing cultural and artistic diversity, as well as fostering peer collaboration and community care.

In my previous paper (Zheng, 2025), I have discussed the importance of sustainable educational and professional development for women at the beginning of their music careers. This paper has provided evidences for the significance of cultivating supportive environments for mid-career female music composers. By learning from the important themes arisen from my analysis, I have contributed further insights into the creation of inclusive and sustainable working environments in music and beyond, for the present and the future.

Across the increasingly competitive industries and professional fields, it is paramount to cultivate sustainable career development for beginning and mid-career professionals, as well as expanding opportunities for collaborations across institutions, cultures, and fields. In future I hope to contribute a more comprehensive discussions on this topic.

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Glossary

- Life stories, Life histories (human research):

In social-psychological research, a life story refers to the detailed experiences, reflections, and perspectives on a person's own life. Life stories entail life narratives employing particular ways of living and cultural activities (Williams, 1985), and the co-production of life stories requires individual and collaborative efforts from both the researcher and each participant (Zheng, 2023). The latter's life is the research focus, but the former's research design also takes effect in shaping the life story.

Thematic life stories, as presented in this paper, focus on particular themes, such as career development, education experiences, etc. Thematic life stories can be drawn from the original data of a life history study or research project (such as my PhD research), but after being analysed into thematic life stories, the data cannot generate life histories (similar to baking).

The main difference between life stories and life histories lies in contextualisation, which adds to the "temporal dimension and developmental dynamic" of life stories (Dhunpath, 2000, p. 546), transforming life stories to life histories. As such, life stories are different from life histories in that, only the latter are contextualised; although the former can be themed (as per this paper) or analysed using other methods (e.g., Goodson, 2016).

Life history research informs organisational, industrial, and other micro- or meso- level, as well as historical, social, cultural, and other macro- level environmental factors that have contributed to the unfolding of human lives. In future I hope to have a further discussion on this topic.

- Portfolio career:

An individual's portfolio career refers to his or her multiple career trajectories. The portfolio usually entails a diverse range of creations or productions, cross-fields, and cross-regional works. Pluralism, collaboration, and openness are key pursuits in cultivating portfolio careers; but such careers are also accompanied by difficulties in achieving personal and family well-beings, or sustainable life and career development. However, developing multiple trajectories in one's career can possibly motivate higher creativity, especially "in a safe and supportive environment" (Hill, 2018, p. 173). My analysis in this paper has evidenced these. Thus, learning and working environments remain the most fundamental influence in having a successful portfolio career.

Declaration

The author declares no conflicts of interest or AI assistance in this work.